

The Influence of Christian Religious Education on Student Behavior

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Abstract

The importance of learning Religious Education, especially Christian Religious Education at Vocational Higher Education following its adherents, to prepare quality and noble human resources in business and industry. It needs to be observed to minimize any deviations in behavior due to reduced religious values in a person. This study aims to describe the learning of Christian Religious Education in Christian Religion courses. Also, it aims to determine the influence of Christian Religious Education learning on student behavior under Christian values. This research uses a quantitative approach with data collection techniques using questionnaires. The value of variable X, namely the influence of Christian religious education learning, is 0.92. It indicates that there is a high or strong influence on learning. Whereas for the Y variable, namely Student Behavior, it is 0.79, indicating a strong influence on student behavior on the study of Christian Religious Education that has been accepted. It means that there is an influence between Christian Religious Education Learning and Student Behavior. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a positive influence on Christian Religious Education Learning and Student Behavior.

1. Introduction

Human civilization in most countries has experienced rapid progress through technology and information, which is increasingly easy to obtain in the palm of one's hand. Luxury and popularity rank at the top in cyberspace. However, it differs from the real world, where something valuable must

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be obtained through struggle. There is a significant quantity of information through technology that some people use all means to get the world's luxuries. Some people are also influenced by the hedonistic view, which in this view considers pleasure and material enjoyment as the main goal in life. It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that there is a deviation in behavior due to a reduction in religious values within a person or what is usually called a moral crisis. According to its adherents, the importance of learning Religious Education, especially Christian Religious Education at Vocational Colleges, is to prepare quality human resources with noble character in business and industry.

Noble morals can be linked to Christian ethics, which has its starting point in Christian anthropology, and Christian anthropology, which has its starting point in Christian theology. Namely an understanding of who humans are in the light of Christian faith. According to Eka Darmaputera[1], at least three things must be said. First, that man is God's creation – therefore, he is good. Second, that man fell into sin – because of that, he was corrupt and evil. Third, that man has been redeemed and justified – therefore, there is hope.

So, if Christian humans believe in the Redeemer, namely Jesus Christ, and carry out all His decrees and commands taught through the holy books, then that human will be good. Humans can be good if they live according to the values of the religion they adhere to.

2. Research Method

The method the author uses in research is a quantitative research method. Data collection techniques use observation, questionnaires, and documentation. The data collection instrument is in the form of a questionnaire or questionnaire. In this classroom action research, the subjects were the fourth-semester students of the Bachelor of Business Administration Study Program, Department of Business Administration, Kupang State Polytechnic, who are Protestant Christians.

3. Results and Discussions

A. Christian Religious Education

Many terms refer to Christian Religious Education according to culture and history in a social environment. Some call it Christian Education or Religious Education, and some call it Christian Religious Education. According to the national curriculum, religious education tertiary institutions receive two Semester Credit Unit weights.

According to the editorial formulation of the Indonesian Church Communion (PGI) in Hasudungan Simatupang et al. [2], first, Christian Religious Education is the deliberate effort of the church to help people of all age groups who are entrusted to its care to respond to God's statements in Jesus Christ, the Bible and the life of the church, so that they, under the guidance of the Holy Spirit, can be equipped to serve God amid family, church, society and society, and natural world. Second, Christian Religious education is an activity that seeks or aims to develop all the potential (ability) of students (both children and adults) to obedience and devotion to God and His word following the teachings of Christianity based on the Bible (Old and New Testaments). Obedience and devotion are expressed in daily life in the family, school, workplace, church, congregation, and society in general.

The importance of Christian Religious Education in Vocational Higher Education, namely preparing students as whole human beings ready to place themselves in the industrial or business world with noble character. Students are also expected to become human beings responsible for their personal life, family, and society.

Educators teach students about Christian Religious Education's learning objectives and take an individual approach. The goal is to understand each student's problems so that, in this way, the right

method can be applied to the students' subject matter. The teacher must be more creative in preparing teaching materials and maximizing individual learning strategies/groups to improve the learning outcomes of Christian Religious Education. Real Didache, Journal of Christian Education Vol.2.[3]

One individual approach for a lecturer is to know the educational background or previous study program. Then, the lecturer can develop his learning strategy because the previous educational background will affect the next learning. Apart from that, there is also a special approach that a lecturer may need to take if some of their students have deviant behavior or are considered inappropriate. In this way, students are expected to get maximum results both academically and by changing their behavior for the better.

According to Mujitahid in his book Jonar T. H. Situmorang[4], Ethics and Professionalism of Christian Religious Education Teachers, a teacher who is considered competent must have eight basic teaching competencies, namely:

1. Manage classes So that the teaching and learning process runs optimally. The teacher's role in creating a classroom atmosphere must be truly ready for a place of learning. If the teacher can organize students and teaching facilities and control them in a pleasant atmosphere, effective learning conditions will be implemented to achieve teaching goals.
2. Skills in explaining material: A teacher must present material orally and organize systematically to show the relationship between one another. Delivery of material that is well planned and presented in a suitable order is a very important aspect of the teacher's activities in his interactions with students in the classroom.
3. Questioning skills: The ability to ask questions is part of the skills and art in the teaching and learning process. In the teaching and learning process, asking questions plays an important role because well-formed questions and appropriate delivery techniques will positively impact students.
4. Skills in opening and closing lessons: To enter a dynamic teaching and learning process, teachers need to create pre-conditions for students so that their minds and attention are focused on what they will learn so that these efforts will positively affect teaching and learning activities. In other words, the activities carried out by the teacher are to create an atmosphere of mental readiness and cause students' attention to focus on the things they are going to learn. This skill aims to arouse students' interest so they are ready to face the problems being studied or discussed.
5. Skills in holding variations: To overcome students' boredom, there are efforts to provide variations so that learning can proceed diligently, enthusiastically, and with full participation.
6. Reinforcement skills: Reinforcement is any verbal or nonverbal response, which is a division of teacher behavior modification towards student behavior, which aims to provide information or feedback to students for their actions as an act of encouragement or correction.
7. Skills in guiding small group discussions: Discussion is one of the methods, ways, or approaches. Group discussions are intended to explore students' thinking potential in solving problems that are the topic of discussion.
8. Individual teaching skills: Interpersonal relationships are established between teachers and students, and vice versa. Students receive assistance from teachers according to their needs and are involved in planning teaching and learning activities.

Thus, a teacher needs to prepare before entering class or giving assignments. The positive energy of a teacher will create much hope for students. A teacher can use different techniques because knowledge will always change according to developments in technology and informatics.

According to Wyckoff in the diktat of the Duta Harapan Malang Christian College regarding the theory and construction of the Christian Religious Education curriculum by Lydia Susanti[5], the design of the Christian Religious Education curriculum is to create learning that can implement the Christian religious learning process according to the existing situation. Design explains the balance of activities and experiences students can learn actively, individually, or in groups.

The individual and group learning process will be used as a learning experience that will produce student attitudes and behavior. Thus, the importance of activities and experiences will determine the final results of Christian religious learning, even though practical learning is lifelong within the body.

A. Behavior

In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, behavior means an individual's response or reaction to stimuli or the environment. Learning itself can be interpreted as changes in behavior or responses caused by experience. However, not all changes in behavior are the result of learning outcomes. Being devout (religious) is one of the basic values of national character education. Education is expected to be able to direct students to become human beings who are devoted to God Almighty.

Yunio Farmelda Sileta Toni, in the Journal of Christian Religious Education Didaktikos[6], said that universal values and religious values can be realized when the assimilation process occurs in teaching and coaching or guiding in a better direction. Assimilation is a renewal or combination of environment or culture and teachings. Another word for assimilation, namely "baptize," is the command of the Lord Jesus to His disciples. It is still related to the word "mission," which means that when searching for what was lost and has been returned, Christian teachers must show repentance and want to become one like the body of Christ. Then, the assimilation process of "baptize" must be carried out to explain the previous situation. They are leaving the old situation and wanting to enter a new situation or life related to faith (spirituality), hoping that Christian teachers will apply assimilation or baptism to restore the condition of converts, especially young people.

The success of Christian religious teaching and education in the classroom can be seen from the behavior or habits of the students themselves. This shows his understanding of religious values, both obtained through learning in the classroom and within the family. Through the teacher's assimilation process in learning for one semester, students are expected to change their behavior for the better.

B. Results

The research results from the data collection process by distributing questionnaires to respondents. The sampling technique in this study used a purposive sampling method, namely a set sample. The size of the sample is determined by the Slovin formula in their book Slamet Rianto and Aglis Andhita Hatmawan[7], namely: $n = \frac{N}{(1+Ne^2)}$

Note:

n = Total Sample

N = Total Population

e = Error rate in sampling

The size of the research sample using the Slovin formula approach will be determined by the error level, where the greater the error rate used, the smaller the number of samples taken. In this study, the error rate was 1% with a total population of 122 people:

$$n = \frac{122}{1+122(0,1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{122}{1+122(0,01)}$$

$$n = \frac{122}{1+1,22}$$

$$n = \frac{122}{2,22}$$

$$n = 54,9$$

Next, it is rounded up to 55 people.

The researchers use a Likert scale to calculate the value and data analysis, and each answer is given its own score. Research scores for 16 positive questions with five alternative answers SS (Strongly Agree) score 5, S (Agree) score 4, R (Undecided) score 3, TS (Disagree) score 2, STS (Strongly Disagree) score 1. Meanwhile, for two negative questions with five alternative answers SS (Strongly Agree) score 1, S (Agree) score 2, R (Undecided) score 3, TS (Disagree) score 4, STS (Strongly Disagree) score 5.

This question was to find out respondents' responses regarding the influence of Christian religious education on the behavior of fourth-semester students majoring in Business Administration at Kupang Polytechnic. This questionnaire is useful for obtaining data, which will then be processed; the results of the respondents' answers will then be recapitulated and analyzed using the following percentage formula:

Formula : $P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$

Note : P = Presentation

F = Frequency

N = Total Respondent

It can be rounded up to 55 people.

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Formula : $P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$

Note : P = Presentation

F = Frequency

N = Total Respondent

Variable (X) Effect of Christian Religious Education Learning.

Based on the results of distributing a questionnaire regarding the Influence of Christian Religious Education Learning on Student Behavior, 55 respondents answered the questionnaire. They obtained

the overall data results, which was processed using the formula: $P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$. The following is a recapitulation table of the overall frequency of variable values (X) as follows:

Recapitulation of the Overall Frequency of Answer Items
The Influence of Learning on Christian Religious Education (X)

Score (S)	Frequency (F)	(S) x (F)
5	277	1385
4	158	632
3	4	12
2	1	2
1	0	0
Total	440	2031

From the table above, it is known that the total score for the Learning Influence variable (X) is a categorization based on the ideal score range, in which:

1. The maximum score is obtained from 5 (highest score) multiplied by the number of statement items multiplied by the number of respondents, i.e., $5 \times 8 \times 55 = 2200$.
2. The minimum score is obtained from 1 (lowest score) times the number of question items times the number of respondents, namely $1 \times 8 \times 55 = 440$. Range of scores = (Maximum score - Minimum score): 5. Thus, the range of scores for the variable Effect of learning (X) = $(2200 - 440) : 5 = 352$. Based on the research results of 55 respondents, the score of the variable Effect of Christian Religious Education Learning (X) of 2031 is included in the high category, or if it is calculated, it is calculated, namely: $= \frac{3031}{2200} \times 100\% = 92,31$ or 0,9231. The value of 0.92, if interpreted, is in the interval 0.80 - 1.00 with a very high level. So, the result of the Influence of Learning on Christian Religious Education (Variable X), namely 92.31, is very high.

Interpretation Guidelines

Coefficient Interval	Relationship Level
0,00 - 0,19	Very low
0,20 - 0,39	Low
0,40 - 0,59	Currently
0,60 - 0,79	Tall
0,80 - 0,1.00	Very high

Based on the calculation results above, it can be concluded that the results of the questionnaire regarding the Influence of Christian Religion Learning are 0.92, which, according to the interval coefficient interpretation guidelines, at a score of 0.80 - 0.1.00, is very high. So, the results of the Influence of Christian Religion Learning questionnaire, which amounted to 0.92, were very high. Thus, student responses regarding Christian Religion Learning are very high.

Variable (Y) Student Behavior

Based on the results of distributing a questionnaire regarding the Influence of Christian Religious Education Learning on Student Behavior, 55 respondents answered the questionnaire. They obtained the overall data results, which was processed using the formula: $P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$. The following is a table recapitulation of the overall variable value frequency (Y) as follows:

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Recapitulation of the Overall Frequency of Student Behavior Answer Items
Knowledge, Attitudes, and Skills (Y)

Score (S)	Frequency (F)	(S) x (F)
5	245	1225
4	171	684
3	40	120
2	59	118
1	35	35
Total	550	2182

From the table above, it is known that the total score for the Student Behavior variable (Y) is a categorization based on the ideal score range, in which:

3. The maximum score is obtained from 5 (highest score) multiplied by the number of statement items multiplied by the number of respondents, namely $5 \times 10 \times 55 = 2750$.
4. The total minimum score is obtained from 1 (lowest score) multiplied by the number of question items multiplied by the number of respondents, $1 \times 10 \times 55 = 550$.

Score range = (maximum score - minimum score): 5. Thus, the range of scores for the Student Behavior variable (Y) = $(2750 - 550) : 5 = 440$

Based on the research results of 55 respondents, the Student Behavior variable score (Y) of 2182 is included in the high category, or if it is a percentage, then it is calculated: $\frac{2182}{2750} \times 100\% = 79,34$ or 0,7934. The value of 0.74, if interpreted, is in the interval 0.60 - 0.79 with a high level. So, the result of Student Behavior (Variable Y) is 79.34, which is considered high.

Interpretation Guidelines

Coefficient Interval	Relationship Level
0,00 - 0,19	Very low
0,20 - 0,39	Low
0,40 - 0,59	Currently
0,60 - 0,79	Tall
0,80 - 0,1.00	Very high

Based on the calculation results above, it is concluded that the results of the questionnaire regarding Student Behavior are 0.79. According to the interval coefficient interpretation guidelines, the score (0.60-0.79) is high. Therefore, the results from the Student Behavior Questionnaire, which is 0.79, are high. It is stated that Christian religious education greatly influences student behavior in the high category.

4. Conclusions

Based on the results of the research and discussion that have been described, it is concluded that the value of variable meanwhile, the Y variable, namely Student Behavior, is 0.79, also indicating that there is a strong influence on student behavior regarding the Christian Religious Education learning that has been received. This means that there is an influence between Christian Religious Education Learning and Student Behavior. So, it can be concluded that there is a positive influence on the research entitled "The Influence of Religious Education Learning on Student Behavior." Studies in semester IV students of the Department of Business Administration, Kupang State Polytechnic.

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